

Disease resistance

Bacterial blight of rice appears to be indigenous on wild rice species in West Africa

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Bacterial blight (BB) of rice in West Africa was found in 1979 in the Sahel region of central Mali in an experiment station, but not in farmers' fields nor in wild rice populations. Unconfirmed reports of BB in introduced paddy rices in the dry areas of Senegal, Niger, and elsewhere in the West African savanna zone occur from time to time.

In September 1980, BB in Cameroun was confirmed on several Asian semi-dwarf varieties in an experimental nursery of the large rice project SEMRY I. The project is near Yagoua along the Logone River in the Sahel-Savanna zone at 10-1/2 degrees north latitude. BB was not detected in the wild annual *O. barthii* but it was found in one small

farmer's hydromorphic rice plot in the Mandara Mountains. This remote site 10 km SW of Mokolo near the Nigerian border was planted to a dryland variety resembling IRAT13 but neither the varietal name nor the seed source could be determined. So far as I am aware, this is the only known instance of BB in West Africa that is not connected with new Asian semidwarfs and with an irrigated paddy project.

Two areas were surveyed in September 1981 to further investigate the possibility of indigenous BB in wild rice or on farming sites: the Mandara foothills north, east, and southwest of Mokolo and the savanna area between Maroua and SEMRY II, 100 km to the northeast of Maroua.

Some hydromorphic dryland rice (*O. sativa*) mixed with *O. glaberrima* and old African dryland (possibly also some IRAT) cultivars is grown in the Mandara hills. No annual wild rice (*O. barthii*) was seen but the perennial *O. longistaminata* is present. No BB was

detected at any of the sites checked, not even in the same farmer's field where BB was found in 1980.

BB was found in many patches of wild *O. barthii* as well as in the less common *O. longistaminata* in the flat savanna NE of Maroua. These areas, near Longi and Bogu, have no native nor introduced rices. They are about 100 km away, without any river connection to the paddy rice project where BB was detected in 1980.

This is evidence that BB is indigenous in the savanna homeland of *O. barthii* and that it is maintaining itself on this annual species and on *O. longistaminata* without any connection to man. It is significant that BB is found only in dry areas similar to those where it has been found in cultivated rice. How widespread the indigenous presence of BB is in West Africa is not known, nor are any details of its epidemiological potential, ecology, off-season survival, or seed transmission. ■

Occurrence of sheath rot in Rajasthan

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Rice sheath rot caused by *Acrocylium drium oryzae* (revised as *Sarocladium oryzae*) was observed at the Rajasthan research station for the first time during the 1981 wet season. The disease was severe at panicle initiation stage in direct-seeded rainfed trials (UVT 1 and PVT 1) of the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad. Rotting occurred at the upper leaf sheath enclosing young panicles. Oblong lesions on the flag leaf coalesced quickly and covered most of the sheath. The disease caused partial exsertion of the panicles, resulting in grain chaffiness. Powdery growth of the fungus was profuse inside affected leaf sheaths.

Infection in different varieties was calculated by counting infected and healthy panicles per unit area. Infected tillers were more than 50% in highly susceptible varieties and 15-20% in moderately susceptible varieties. Of 73 varieties, 7 showed a clearly susceptible reaction and 14 were moderately susceptible. The varieties and their reaction to sheath rot are:

Highly susceptible: CR141-7639, CRRP 2, IR9204-117-2-3-3-2, RP1422-2-1-2-3, RP1422-2-1-3-4, RP1422-2-2-3-2, RP1422-2-2-3-5, and KP1670-1418-2205-1582.

Moderately susceptible: CR222MW10, OR83-23, BK664, CR215-55-54-1, CR289-1208, RAU3-4-1, RP1674-4038-78-4, RP1899-1689-98, RP1899-1481-78-1, RP1451-1712-4319, RP1888-4254-1529-126, RP1670-4221-1585-2205-1418-3, Ad 98, and Rewa 353. ■

Phytoalexin production in the incompatible reaction of rice to *Pyricularia oryzae*

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The synthesis of antifungal compounds of phytoalexins by plants in response to incompatible races or species of fungal parasites is considered an important mechanism of resistance to fungal infection. Diterpenoid phytoalexins (momilactones A and B) have been isolated from blast-infected leaves of normally susceptible rice cultivar Sasashigure after treatment with 2,2-dichloro-3, 3-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid. This fungicide is considered to activate natural resistance mechanisms, including an increased capacity to produce phytoalexins. ■